

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B210
Date: 13th June 2006
Take Off: 13:54:03
Landing: 17:17:11
Flight Time: 3h23m08

Campaign: CAPEX (CLAPREC)
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Beja - Lisbon and over ocean

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Danny Rosenfeld	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
7	Core Chemistry	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
9	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
10	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
11	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
12	Wet Neph / PSAP	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
15	CLAPREC 1	Regina Corte-Real	University of Evora
16	CLAPREC 2	Susanna Mendes	University of Evora
17	CLAPREC 3	Sergio Pereira	University of Evora
18	EUFAR Training	Piotr Drzewicki	University of Warsaw
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B210 Track 13-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b210
 Date: 13 Jun 2006
 Project: CAPEX CLAPREC
 Location: Beja - Lisbon and over ocean

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
132927		event	0.65 kft	095	INU to Nav
134342		Start-Up 4	0.65 kft	095	
134808		event	0.65 kft	095	start taxi
135403		T/O	0.79 kft	185	Beja
135440	140820	Profile 1	1.1 - 10.0 kft	185	from T/O
135858		in cloud	4.6 kft	232	
140013		Video	5.2 kft	233	start DFC FFC
140128		out cl	5.8 kft	244	
140333		event	6.7 kft	240	jw cal
140355		event	7.1 kft	235	nev cal
140441		in c	7.8 kft	236	
140551		out cl	8.2 kft	231	
140849	141040	Run 1.1	10.0 kft	217	140820
140917		out cl	10.0 kft	218	
141152	141805	Profile 2	10.0 - 4.0 kft	265	
141851	142455	Profile 2	4.1 - 0.32 kft	278	
142456	142556	Run 2.1	0.32 - 0.30 kft	293	
142607	142657	Profile 3	0.44 - 1.0 kft	302	
142838	143437	Run 3.1	1.1 kft	216	
143656	144541	Profile 3	1.1 - 5.0 kft	314	p4
144108		event	3.0 kft	283	reset core DLU
144813	144922	Profile 5	5.0 - 5.6 kft	167	at start in cl
144848		out cl	5.5 kft	168	
145035	145122	Run 4.1	5.6 kft	073	
145100		out cl	5.6 kft	069	stat in cl
145143	145758	Profile 6	5.6 - 10.0 kft	068	
145759	145931	Run 5.1	10.0 kft	075	
145849		nev zero	10.0 kft	076	
145928		event	10.0 kft	075	
150052		event	10.0 kft	077	jw zero
151310		event	6.1 kft	104	jw zero
151428	151553	Profile 7	6.0 - 6.8 kft	146	
151651	151857	Profile 7	6.7 - 7.7 kft	147	
152216	152249	Profile 7	7.7 - 8.0 kft	349	
152631	152855	Profile 7	8.0 - 10.0 kft	347	
153015	153158	Run 6.1	10.0 kft	267	
153209	153448	Profile 8	10.0 - 12.0 kft	261	
153317		Video	10.9 kft	261	change
153521	153829	Run 7.1	12.0 kft	090	
153740		in cl	12.0 kft	082	
153819		out cl	12.0 kft	111	
154143	154312	Run 8.1	14.0 kft	348	
154204		in cl	14.0 kft	344	
154257		out	14.0 kft	278	
154549		event	16.1 kft	353	jw zero
154922	155015	Run 9.1	18.1 - 17.8 kft	030	
154932		in cl	18.2 kft	008	
155013		out cl	17.8 kft	283	
155310	155553	Run 10.1	20.0 kft	108	
155429		in cl	20.0 kft	026	
161340		nev zero	22.0 kft	347	
161440		jw ca	22.0 kft	346	
161714	161922	Run 11.1	22.0 kft	008	
161723		out	22.0 kft	006	
161845		in	22.0 kft	289	
161919		out	22.0 kft	281	
162251	162418	Run 12.1	24.0 kft	027	
162350		in cl	24.0 kft	031	
162409		out	24.0 kft	031	
162711	162912	Run 13.1	26.1 - 26.0 kft	199	

162735		in cl	25.9 kft	201
162906		out cl	26.0 kft	210
163411	163812	Run 14.1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	345
163536		in cl	28.0 kft	345
163730		in cl	28.0 kft	002
164308		in clop	20.5 kft	196
164414		in clop	18.0 kft	173
164507		in clop	16.8 kft	188
164621		in clop	15.2 kft	188
164634		incclo	14.9 kft	188
164657		in clop	14.3 kft	187
164837		in clop	12.3 kft	179
165216	170747	Run 15.1	8.0 kft	147
170812	171802	Profile 9	7.7 - 0.70 kft	348 at end run 171711
171802	171810	Land	0.70 kft	116 171711
172132		Shutdown	0.68 kft	089 38 05.13N 7 55.65W

B210 Track 13-JUN-06

11°W

10°W

9°W

8°W

7°W

40°N

40°N

39°N

39°N

38°N

38°N

37°N

37°N

11°W

10°W

9°W

8°W

7°W

B210 SORTIE BRIEF (Deep convection)

Aerosol Cloud Interaction Sortie (CLAPREC). 13th June 2006

Necessary weather conditions:

Convective clouds over Portugal growing through the 10 kft level.

Trial Objectives:

- To measure vertical profiles of cloud microstructure and precipitation forming processes.
- To document aerosols from natural & anthropogenic sources & relate these to cloud composition and precipitation processes.

Location:

1. Central/S. Portugal
2. Over ocean to the SW of Lisbon

Take Off: 1400L, will be delayed if deep convection is not reported by 1200L. Latest landing time is 1900L.

Flight Pattern:

Part 1: Over land

1. Climb northward to 10 kft for identifying the area of cloud activity. (10 minutes)
2. Expedite descend to below cloud base level (estimated 5 kft) and fly to the working area while measuring CCN. (25 minutes)
3. At the work area profile upward through convective clouds. In the case of Cb, concentrate at the upshear feeders. (40 minutes)
4. Terminate upward cloud profile at cloud top level or top of clouds that contain LWC, whatever comes first. Probable highest level in favourable conditions would be 25 kft.

Part 2: Over ocean

We will be able to see potential clouds of interest over the ocean while finishing the cloud profile ascend. If there will be clouds of interest, we will:

1. Fly to an ocean area to the south of Lisbon TMA, doing one CCN spectrum aloft. (10 minutes)
2. After completion of the CCN, expedite to transit air speed, aiming to reach the cloud top altitude over ocean. (20 minutes)
3. Do downward profile through convective clouds. (30 minutes)
4. Do aerosol profile below cloud base descending at 500 fpm, reaching momentarily down to 50 feet. (5 minutes)
5. Do CCN spectrum at 1000 feet while heading home over ocean. Do not cross coastline into land before finishing the CCN spectrum. (10 minutes)
6. Continue towards base alternating between cloud base +1000 feet and cloud base -1000 feet.
7. Landing. (25 minutes).

Total flight time 175 minutes.

Part 2 alternate if there are no suitable clouds over ocean:

1. Fly back to base, while doing CCN spectrum aloft. (10 minutes)
2. Continue descend to base through clouds of opportunity after finishing the CCN spectrum. (25 minutes).

Total flight time 110 minutes.

Research flight: 13 June 2006 Afternoon, CALPREC Portugal

Objectives:

Document convective vertical profiles of aerosols and clouds over ocean and over land.

Crew aircraft 1:

Pilots:

Flight scientist: Daniel Rosenfeld

Instruments operators:

Synoptic conditions:

An upper low cutoff just to the SW of Portugal draws Sahara air with dust from the SSE aloft and oceanic air at the levels below 5 kft. A cyclonic spiral band of elevated convection developed during the day and produced thunderstorms over land and Lisbon that we profiled. At the lower level marine clouds with continental microstructure occurred over ocean, with some convection induced by the closed low level circulation just off the coast of Lisbon. We measured these clouds as well.

Flight report for Aircraft 1:

We took off as at 13:52 and ascended westward, crossing lowest cloud base at 4700'. We continued ascending 500 fpm through cloud layers that were not vertically connected up reaching 10 kft at 14:07. We continued westward and passed through tops of few castellanus with bases at about 9500'. There were broken cirrus clouds above. The visibility was poor (10-15 km) apparently due to desert dust haze, but improved significantly when we flew west. The air over ocean looked pristine, and we could see the Cb developing some 100 miles to the west.

We descended profiling downward through cloud tops at 5000' at 14:18, reaching 250' at the bottom. We returned to 1000' and continued flying westward, going to do CCN measurement. As we were collecting the sample we encountered a low cloud with base below our flight level that rained (14:25). We diverted to the south of the rain resampling the CCN, in what appeared to be still in cloud. This compromised the CCN measurement. We abandoned the CCN measurement at 14:36 and start ascending profiling through the clouds over ocean SW of Lisbon, reaching to convective looking cloud tops at 5500', capped under a very strong and sharp inversion of 5 degrees, with extremely dry air (DP=-15C) above a nearly saturated air mass below (14:51). The CNC counts were down to 300 cm⁻³ and ozone showed very high values (to verify with Keith). Was it stratospheric air descending at the downward part of the center of the closed circulation? The 7.3 μm water vapor MSG image supports this suggestion. No taller clouds could be

seen in the approximate area that was raining at the low levels, so that this rain must have been created below the inversion level by warm processes.

We continued eastward toward working at the upshear feeders of a Cb line that appeared at the coastline to the south of Lisbon. We descended to 6000' to get to the cloud base. When we approached the location of that cloud just inland (15:27) the visibility deteriorated considerably, and multilayer cloud structure prevented us to have a good fix on the feeder clouds to the Cb cluster. We passed the cloud line and realizing that we can't see much, we came back and positioned ourselves to the south of the echoes while ascending through the barely discernible clouds in the haze.

At 12 kft (15:38) we approached the main Cb and started circling and staircase profiling it upward at 2 kft intervals. The cloud drifted northward on the airways feeding to Lisbon airport quite close to the city. We had to get permission for each turn, but the flight controller gave us all that we needed. We kept profiling upward cutting through the shoulder of the feeders quite active Cb just outside the echoing areas, and managed to stay out of intense precipitation while still logging high LWC of up to 0.9 g m⁻³ on the JW, and 1.0 on the Nevzorov.

At 22 kft we tried to move to a more southeastern cloud cluster, while letting the crew out of the belts and refresh, and getting away from Lisbon. But ATC held us from turning into the clouds for too long until they collapsed on our way back north, and eventually we resumed passing in our original cloud, that now was even closer to Lisbon.

At 16:16 we passed through a small isolated growing top at 22 kft on the way to the feeder of the main Cb, where we got a brief intense graupel. At 24 kft (16:23) we passed through an intensely growing isolated cloud that was quite vigorous and had a peak JW LWC of 0.8 g m⁻³ at T=-25C. On a retrack return to it from the north at 26 kft the cloud was already glaciated just after three minutes (16:26). We returned to the cloud once more at 28 kft just to validate that there were no more water. This was also the highest that we could get some performance from the aircraft during these challenging conditions.

We finished the upward profile there (16:38) and started profiling down southward towards Beja through clouds of opportunity. There were nice succession of young cloud towers that we penetrated on the way down, until we emerged through cloud base at 9500'. Below was a lower cloud that was likely below the top of the inversion, so we leveled at 8000' and started a CCN run (16:52-17:03). After that we profiled downward at 1000 fpm and landed at Beja at 17:17.

The debriefing was done with cheese and wine party in thanks giving for the support of personnel of the Beja air force base.

Impressions

We apparently went smack through the two contrasting part of a synoptic scale cyclone, moving from the downward forced part that occurred over ocean to the upward forced part over land. The convection appeared to be disconnected from the boundary layer,

feeding on air that was advected mainly at 8-15 kft from the Sahara. The clouds over land contained much water only in the very intense updrafts, but glaciated fast in the less active parts and above 22 kft. Was this due to the ice nucleating activity of the desert dust?

Mission Scientist's Log

T ^{Daniel} R

Daniel Rosenfeld

Flight No **B.210**

Date **13.6.2006**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:43					ignition wind calm
13:52					Take off
13:54	Profile 1	1800			Start profile up 1000 fpm up to base
13:58		4720	cbcs		Visibility ~ 15 km, dust haze
13:59		5300			Ascend 500 fpm in clouds
14:07		10000			M ₃ poorly defined top of 10000
14:11		10000			Descend to 5000
14:13		8000			Brown aerosol layer
14:18		5000			cloud top height descend ...
14:28		10000			Rain U+perm CCN prof. 10
14:36		1000			500 fpm in clouds
14:38		9200			in cloud no echo
14:43		4000			in convective tops
14:54		6000			Go west to work over land
15:27					approaching Cb from south
15:43		120		140	0.7 JW
15:46		140			0.5 JW
15:48		160			0.7 JW
15:48		180			0.7 JW
15:53		200			0.3 JW
15:57		220			Go to new cloud to 170 30 miles
16:09		220			returning north to cloud 2.
16:16		220			0.5
16:18		220			graupel 0.7
16:23		240			
16:26		260			rised very much and a bit glaciated 0.05

Mission Scientist's Log

CHAPREC (#2)

(Denny R MSc 1)
(Dek MSc 2)

Flight No **B.210**

Date **13/6/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1354					T/O BEJA. (RW19)
					8/8 AcAsCs above. Hazy.
135403					Start P1. 1000' / mi
1357	P1	4.0 kft	232°	37° 48' N 8° 0' W	Rate of climb to 500' / mi
135840					Running along cloud.
135900					Into cloud now.
140013		5.2 kft			Between cloud layers
140445	P1	7.7 kft	235°	37° 36' N 8° 30' W	Into thin cloud now, P1 now 500' / mi
140550		8.4 kft	→		Between layers, incr. rate of climb to 1000' / mi
140820	D1 / R1.1	10.0 kft	217°		End P1 / Start R1.1
140930			→	37° 24' N 8° 48' W	Out of cloud just over coast now (N of SW tip of Portugal)
141040			→		End R1.1. Descend to FLOSO.
141152	P2	10.0 kft	265°	37° 18' N 9° 00' W	Start P2 ↓
141851	D2	3.7 kft	279°	37° 16' N 9° 36' W	Recomm. P2 ↓ WIND 105° / 10 m/sec
142456	END P2 START R	250'	276°	37° 24' N 10° 6' W	END P2, START R, 250' Climb to 1000'.
142556	END R1 START P3	250'	307°		Climb to 1000', soon into cloud
	END P3 START R	1000'			End P2, Start R Into rain, too to not cloud, take CCW sample
142755			→		End Run, turn L to avoid cloud.
~ 142845		1000'			Start R3.1 (in turn) 1 CCW sample
142940					Wings SEL
143437	END R3.1	1000'		37° 6' N 10° 6' W	End R3.1, turn ↓. S. POINT ~5-7°C HIGHER THAN DET. (at T/S)
					WIND 091° / 13 m/sec
143656	START P4	1000' ↑	315°	37° 12' N 10° 12' W	Start P4 ↑ through cloud up to FLO70

Mission Scientist's Log (#2)

 Flight No **B.210**

 Date **13/6/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					* Temp off-scale *
					DIT reset; now tracking DIT.
144541	END P4.	FLO50 (1012)	075	37° 30' N 10° 36' W	End P4.
					In more convection generally in this area.
144813	START P5	FLO50	167°	37° 24' N 10° 36' W	Start P5, as enter class at 1000'/min
					Now level
144922		FLO50			End P5, head back towards Beja.
145033	END P5	FLO50	070°	37° 18' N 10° 36' W	LOW THRU CLOUD
145125	END P5				OUT OF CLOUD. (145057)
145143			072°		Start P1, up to FL100
	[DID NOT HAVE CHANCE TO WORK				SEE END ^H ABOVE CLOUD LEG - TOO MUCH CI ABOVE]
145749	END S-1	FL100	075°	37° 30' N 9° 54' W	Start Run at FL100 160°/17 m/sec.
145931	END S-1				End Run AT FL100 [into CCM STRIKE] (NO PROFILE)
					W.11 descended to FL060, then go thro
					Line of convection S → N, ascending.
151130					Start Turn ↗ into 360°.
					(Choose alternative line of C)
151428	START P7.	FL060	146°	37° 36' N 8° 30' W	Start P7 500'/min, then 1000'/min thro class
					Wind 160°/7 m/sec.
151553					Interrupt P7.
151651	Restart P7.	FL067	147°	..	Recommence P7
151867		FL077			Interrupt P7., turning ↘
152216		FL077	348°	37° 30' N 8° 24' W	Comb (P7)
152249		FL080			Interrupt P7 (End)
					Heading: NNW.

Water. [J/W].

Mission Scientist's Log (#2)

Flight No **B**.....210.....

Date 13/6/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152637	P7.	FL 80	348°	37° 48' N 8° 30' W	Recommend P7.
152855	P7	FL 100			Interrupt P7 flight, Turn onto W heading
153015	RW 6.1	FL 100	264°	38° 01' N 8° 36' W	Start R 6.1.
1532	End 6.1 / Start P8	FL 100	261°		End 6.1, start P8 / FL 120.
					Can turn during climb, back onto E to run thro' feeders at FL 120.
153448	End P8	FL 120	084°		End P8 at FL 120
153521	Start 7.1		075°		Start (FL 120) RW 7.1.
					End RW 7.1, do climbing & head back at FL 140
153743					Into cloud. (J/W up to $> 0.7 \text{ gm}^{-3}$)
~ 153829		→	End RW		Turning R, reciprocal
154143	Start 28.1	FL 140	339°	38° 12' N 8° 36' W	Start R 28.1
1541					Into cloud.
154312	End 28.1	FL 140			End 28.1, out of cloud go left & climb to FL 160 (J/W up to 0.5 gm^{-3})
1545		FL 160	←	Orbit	Start 28.1 at FL 160
1546			←		Into cloud. [(J/W) peak at 0.7 gm^{-3}]
154908			→		E Now at FL 180.
		FL 180		About to	Enter cloud. Start R 9.1 (J/W) 0.7 gm^{-3}
155015					End R 9.1 / Orbit.
1552					Climbing ↑ FL 200.
155310		FL 200	107°	38° 12' N 8° 36' W	Start R 10.1
155431		FL 200			Into cloud. (J/W) Max 0.3 gm^{-3}
155553					End R 10.1.

MSg from GEFJ
 1430Z VIS
 1500Z IR satpics

Mission Scientist's Log (#2)

Mo Best choice.

CBs + 35.5W 8.3W
 + 40.5W 8.3W
 SPECIES N of 38°N over Portugal
 Flight No **B 210**

Date 13/6/06

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1609					Repositioning for next line of Cu/Cb
1614		FL220	346°	38° 12' N 8° 12' W	Still repositioning Wind 140°/23kts ⁻¹
					transit to next convective area at higher speed.
161530			→		Slowing speed now.
161717					into cloud tops } J/W 0.5 g/m ³
161722					Out of cloud }
161714	11-1	FL220	347°	38° 36' N 8° 24' W	Start R 11-1
161850			→		into cloud J/W 0.7 g/m ³
161928	11-1	FL220			End R 11-1
162251	12-1	FL240	028°	38° 36' N 8° 24' W	Start R 12-1 Wind 158°/25kts
162358					Enter cloud. J/W 0.8 g/m ³
162405					Out of cloud
162418	END R 12-1	FL240			End R 12-1
162711	START 13-1				Start R 13. J/W 0.8 g/m ³
162		FL260			in cloud
162912					End R 13.
1634.			←		Climb to FL280.
1634	14-1	FL280			Start R 14. J/W - no discernable EWC here
163536	"		345°		into cloud now FL280
163745					Again into cloud.
163812					End 14-1, Turning ↓ descend to low level for run at ~5000' (under cloud).
164230					Descending to FLOS, will penetrate some Cu/Cb on way down.
164311		19.9kft	→		into cloud J/W 0.9 g/m ³

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B210

Date : 13/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Background ppbV became very high above FL150, resulting in unreliable data, especially during profile descent after calibration at FL220. Some testing was done in flight to try to rectify the problem – this may affect data.
O₃	None
NO_x	No flow through Ozonator at FL150 and above therefore only NO channel available (no NO₂ or NO_x measurements). Flow did not recover on descent until FL100.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

CCN LOG

T6

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT FT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		1000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
14:27 14:28	14:29/16		25.8	0.16					S Noosed -
									D Sample taken in cloud on
									B Mission Sci's instruction.
									R 'B' reading 4095
									P Chamber inspect
									Profile Run @ 12000'
14:33 14:32	14:33	2678	2478	0.17	0.30	0.50	0.69	1.07	S Sample taken
		2691	247	910	807	2082	2406	2866	D @ 1000' then climbed
Start of analysis		2692	2316	675	675	716	742	852	B to when sample analysed
@ 10000		2688	22.38	2408	2457	2448	2447	2458	R Held in alleviator awaiting Miss Sci instruction
15:31:15		2688	21.24	977.7	967.3	964.7	964.7	964.8	P to analyse on Run
on Miss Sci instruction									Start of prog 2
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
16:30	16:34	2633	24.09	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.70	1.06	S Not a run
		2623	2324	189	611	136	2593	267	D Analysis requested by Miss Sci
		2597	2224	137	148	136	171	177	B Analysis in bumpy cloud.
Completed		26.12	21.8	2366	2369	2375	2578	2382	R
16:22:00		25.91	20.40	886.0	886.1	886.4	885.9	876.1	P
		8000'							
165216	165301	26.52	28.25	0.17	0.30	0.48	0.69	1.07	S Run
		26.48	23.81	1057	1084	1328	1449	1891	D
		26.44	22.85	840	857	807	814	865	B 15
		26.25	21.8	2390	2396	240	2402	2406	R
Completed		26.33	20.8	987.5	989.5	989.5	989.5	989.5	P
17:07	38			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	13/6/06	Flight	B210	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAPEX			
Departure	Beja	Arrival	Beja			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on				at time		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	21	Ch	21	Ch18	22
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on				at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time		
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual		•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software				at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	305.9	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	42.8	34.2	36.8	40.0	40.5	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again				at time		

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.210** CAPEX
CLAPREC
FLIGHT

 Date 13/06/06

 Operator's name: WILSON

 Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
123000								Pre flight zeros OK.
								Claprec scientist requests wet neph to be run at scrape max humidity for this sortie.
135422								take off from Beja, Portugal.
135440	P1							start P1
140820	P1	FL100	13.0	22	73	↗	40	end P1 @ FL100
140849	R1.1	"						
141040	R1.1	"	13.3	17	71	—	40	end R1.1
141152	P2	FL100 ↘	13.3	17.1	73	—	40	start P2 → 5000ft.
141458	---	FL065	11.9	25	74	↗	40	set water temp to +43C
141805	P2	4000ft						int P2
141851	P2	4000ft ↘						restart P2
142155	P2	2000ft	14.6	64	87	→	43°C	
142456	P2/R2.1	250ft	14.3	79	91	→	43°C	end P2 and start R
142560	R2.1/P3	250ft						
142657	R3	1000ft	14.2	81	93	→	43	end P3 @ 1000ft
142838	R3.1	1000ft	14.2	80	93.6	—	---	start R3.1
142950		1000ft	14.3	79	93.7	↘	43	set water to 42C
143218		1000ft	14.3	78	93	↘	42	set water to +40C
143437	R3.1	---	14.4	76	90.5	→	40	end R3.1

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B** 210.....

Date 13/06/06.....

Operator's name: WILSON.....

Page 2 of 4.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
143656	P4	1000ft ↗	14.4	80	90.9	→	40	start P4
144541	P4	5000ft	12.2	51	88	→	40	end P4.
144813	P5	---						start P5
144922	P5	5600ft	12.2	36	86	→	40	end P5
145035	P4.1	5600ft		21	83	→	40	start P4.1
145132	---	5600ft	12.2	20	82	---	---	end P4.1
145143	P6	--- ↗	12.2	19	81	---	---	start P6
145758	P6	FL100						end P6
145769	P5.1	---	11.5					start P5.1
145931	P5.1	---	11.5	28	81	→	40	end P5.1
150600	—							descending to FL060. set water to +42C
151428	P7	FL060 ↗	12.2	48	86	→	42C	start P7
151553	P7	FL068	11.9	51	88	→	42C	int P7
151651	---	FL068	11.8	51	88.7	---	---	restart P7
151857	---	FL077	11.5	48	89	---	---	int P7 @ FL077. Turning reciprocal.
152216	---	---	11.5	47	89.7	---	---	restart P2
152249	---	FL080	11.3	47	90	---	---	int P7
152631	---	---	11.1	46	91	---	---	restart P7
152855	P7	FL100	12.9	36	88	---	---	end P7 @ FL100
153015	P6.1	---	13.0	34	87.4	→	42C	start P6.1

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.210**.....

 Date **13/06/06**.....

 Operator's name: **Wilson**.....

 Page **3** of **4**..

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
153208	R6.1/P8	FL100 →	12.9	29	86	→	42c	end R6.1, start P8 → FL120.
153448	P8	FL120						end P8
153521	R7.1	FL120	12.1	21	86	→	42c	start R7.1
153829	R7.1	120	12.1	23	86	-"-	-"-	end R7.1
154143	R8.1	FL140	11.3	8	85	-"-	-"-	start R8.1
154245	-"-	140	11.2	15	86	-"-	-"-	in cloud !!
154312	R8.1			8	85	-"-	-"-	end R8.1. now climbing to FL160.
154922	R9.1	FL180	10.4	3	87	-"-	-"-	start R9.1
155019	-"-	-"-	10.4	3	87	-"-	-"-	end R9.1
155310	R10.1	FL200	10.0	3	88	-"-	-"-	start R10.1
155358	-"-	-"-	9.8	3.7	89	-"-	42c	in cloud - bumpy.
155553	R10.1		9.6	4	90	-"-	-"-	end R10.1
161923	R11.1	FL220	11.0	0	86	→	42	start R11.1
161922	R11.1	-"-	11.0	0	86	→	42	end R11.1
162251	R12.1	FL240	10.2	0	87.7	→	42	start R12.1
162400	-"-	-"-	10.2	0	88	→	42	in cloud !
162418	R12.1	FL240	10.1	0	88.5	→	42	end R12.1
162711	R13.1	FL260	10.5	0	90	→	42	start R13.1
162800	R13.1	FL260	10.6	0	89.7	-"-	-"-	in cloud.
162912	R13.1	-"-	-"-	0	87.4	-"-	-"-	end R13.1

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B	Date	Operat or(s)	log page	1	of	1
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

1026						Set laptop time = DRS			
						Sws video u/s			
135405						T/o Beja			
1359			shims	50	200	Shims ok		x	
1401	P1		Zen + 6	50	200	Sws ok, in cloud	x		
140820	R1.1					End profile, start run			
141040						End run			
141152	P2	FL100	Zen + 6	50	200	Start profile	x		
1412			shims	50	200			x	
1420			Zen + 6	30	200		x		
142457	R2	250' asl	Zen + 6	30	200	End profile, start run			
142558	P3					End run, start profile			
1428?	R3	1000' asl	Zen + 6	30	200	start run, in out cloud, cloud above			
143438						End run			
143651	P4	1000' asl	Zen + 6	30	200	Start profile			
144541		5000'				End profile			
144814	P5	5000'	Zen +6	30	200	Start profile			
144922		FL55				End profile			
						Chaotic flight pattern, cloud above, below and all round			
145800	R5	FL100	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run, cloud above and below	x		
1458		FL100	shims	50	200				
1459						End run			
151429	P7	FL60	Zen + 6	30	200	Start profile, cloud all around	x		
1515			shims	50	200			x	
153015	R6	FL100	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run, in/out of cloud, cloud above			
153209	P8					End run start profile			
1534		FL120				End profile			
153520	R7	FL120	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run, cloud above and below	x		
1535			shims	50	200			x	
153829						End run			
154145	R8	FL140				Start run, cloud all around			
154312						End run			
154922	R9	FL180	Zen +6	30	200	Start run	x		
155015						End run			
155310	R10	FL200	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run			
155553						End run			
161714	R11	FL220	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run			
161922						End run			
162253	R12	FL240	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run, Ci above			
162418						End run			
162711	R13	FL260	"	"	"	Start run			
162912						End run			
163411	R14	FL280	"	"	"	Start run, some ci above			
163812						End run, water evident on scanner window			
165216	R15	FL80	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run, cloud all round			
170733						End run, instruments off			
171711						Land Beja			

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 210 Date: 13th June 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	Y
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI (incl PCASP)	Y
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera	N		
TAFTS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
MARSS	Y	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	N
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N